
Future of Collaborative Analysis Using Mixed Reality

Fig.1- Future of Mixed Reality

Overview of the current state of AR and VR

The use of augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) in creating collaboration environments has been gaining traction in recent years. These immersive environments have been used to create unique collaborative experiences and improve the sharing of situational and navigational information among users. In particular, AR has been found to be useful in reproducing some of

the spatial cues used in face-to-face collaboration that are normally lost in remote conferencing systems, increasing social presence compared to other technologies, and allowing remote collaborators to interact naturally in the local user's real environment.

One example of how AR has been used in remote collaboration is the development of a remote collaborative visualization system that utilizes mixed reality techniques to provide co-presence, information sharing, and collaborative analysis functions for users at different locations. This system has been found to be effective in promoting efficient and effective collaboration among users in different locations, as it allows them to share and analyze data in a more comprehensive way. This is particularly useful for complex problems that require multiple perspectives and expertise, such as environmental pollution.

Other examples of AR collaboration systems include co-located AR systems for supporting joint planning tasks by providing shared organization-specific views for police and military personnel, and tabletop fiducial AR systems for co-located collaboration. These systems demonstrate the versatility and effectiveness of AR in promoting collaboration and information sharing among users.

There are a variety of devices that utilize AR and VR technology for creating immersive collaboration environments. Some of the most popular devices include:

1. Head-mounted displays (HMDs) such as the Oculus Rift, HTC Vive, and PlayStation VR, which are worn on the head and provide a fully immersive experience.
2. Smartphones and tablets, which can be used with AR apps and accessories such as the HoloLens, Google Glass, and Meta 2, to overlay digital information onto the real world.
3. Smart glasses, such as the Vuzix Blade and North Focals, which are worn like regular eyeglasses and project digital information directly in the user's field of view.
4. Room-scale VR systems, such as the Oculus Quest and Valve Index, which allow users to move around in a physical space while wearing a VR headset.
5. AR and VR headsets for enterprise, such as the Microsoft HoloLens, which are designed specifically for business use cases and provide enhanced features like hand gestures and voice commands.
6. Standalone VR systems, such as the Oculus Go and Quest, which do not require a PC or console to run, and can be used wirelessly.

These devices offer a wide range of features and capabilities, from fully immersive VR experiences to overlaying digital information onto the real world. The choice of device will depend on the specific needs and requirements of the collaboration environment. For example, a room-scale VR system would be ideal for a training simulation, while a smart glass would be more suitable for a field worker who needs to access digital information while on the job

How do I start developing AR applications?

Developing AR applications can be a complex process, but there are several ways to approach it. Some of the most common ways to develop AR applications include:

1. Using pre-built AR development platforms such as Unity, Vuforia, and ARKit, which provide the necessary tools and resources for creating AR applications. These platforms offer various features like image recognition, tracking, and 3D modeling, and have large developer communities that share tutorials and examples.
2. Building AR applications using game engines such as Unity or Unreal Engine, which provide a wide range of tools and resources for creating interactive 3D environments.
3. Developing AR applications using programming languages such as C++, Java, and C#, which offer more control over the application's functionality and performance. This approach is more suitable for developers with a strong programming background.
4. Using open-source libraries and frameworks like OpenCV, ARToolKit, and ARKit, which can be used to create AR applications with a range of features like image tracking, marker detection, and 3D rendering.
5. Using cloud-based AR development platforms like Amazon Sumerian, which allows developers to create AR and VR applications without needing to have in-depth knowledge of programming languages or 3D modeling.

Ultimately, the choice of method will depend on the specific needs and requirements of the AR application, as well as the skills and experience of the development team. Some developers may prefer to use pre-built platforms, while others may prefer to use programming languages or game engines.

Advancements in the field of Mixed Realities

Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) technology have come a long way in recent years, with a number of advancements being made in both fields. Some of the most notable advancements in VR and AR include:

1. Improved hardware: VR and AR headsets have become more lightweight, compact and powerful, with higher resolution displays and improved field of view. Handheld controllers have also become more precise and intuitive, allowing for more immersive experiences.
2. Inside-out tracking: Inside-out tracking is a technology that allows VR and AR headsets to track the user's position and movements without the need for external cameras or sensors. This makes the devices more portable and easier to set up.
3. Wireless VR: With the advent of 5G networks, the future of VR is wireless. The new wireless VR headsets are more convenient and less restricting, providing a more immersive experience.
4. Increased interactivity: Advancements in hand and finger tracking, haptic feedback, and eye-tracking technology have allowed for more realistic and intuitive interactions in VR and AR environments.
5. Improved graphics: With the advances in VR and AR technology, graphics have become more realistic, detailed and lifelike, providing an immersive experience for users.
6. Spatial audio: Spatial audio technology provides a more immersive audio experience for VR and AR, by simulating sound in 3D space, allowing users to hear sounds from different directions, and to feel like they are in a real physical space.

7. Extended Reality (XR): XR is an umbrella term that refers to a combination of VR, AR, and mixed reality (MR). XR

In conclusion, the use of AR and VR in creating collaboration environments¹ is a promising area of research, as it has been found to be effective in improving the sharing of situational and navigational information among users, and promoting efficient and effective collaboration among remote users. As technology continues to advance, we can expect to see more innovative and effective uses of AR and VR in collaboration systems in the future. The article below proposes a great way for information sharing through AR/VR devices.

¹ (n.d.). Improving Information Sharing and Collaborative Analysis for Retrieved January 20, 2023, from <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8943760>